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CRONUS

CAPTURE AND REUSE OF BIOGENIC GASES FOR NEGATIVE-EMISSION – SUSTAINABLE BIOFUELS

The overall ambition of the CRONUS project is to significantly advance the current state of the art in the area of biofuels production and the utilisation of biogenic effluent gases. CRONUS will introduce effective technologies with high-potential innovations (techno-economic feasible solutions), thus accelerating the green transition and associated transformation of our economy, industry and society with a view to achieving climate neutrality in Europe by 2050.

CRONUS aims to accelerate on the path to sustainable bioenergy and play an important and constructive role in achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, by incorporating in the biofuels production lines Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage (CCUS) techniques. CCUS can stand as a solution to meet the 2021 Glasgow agreement on climate change's aim of less than 1,5°C and contribute to the phase-out of fossil fuels and the decarbonisation of the EU economy in accordance to European Green Deal goals.

Project Objectives

CRONUS addresses the current gaps in biofuels production, namely the carbon waste and biogenic effluent gases and their related environmental problems by implementing optimised management systems whilst having a positive trade-off with productivity, quality and environmental impact. The overall objective of CRONUS is to develop 5 Functional Prototypes to assess and test 5 new integrated and sustainable technological solutions for highly efficient biogenic effluent gases CUS within the biofuels value chain.

Thus, by the cutting-edge sustainable innovations proposed in terms of techno-economic feasible solutions, CRONUS will assure biofuels' public and regulators acceptance and market incursion. CRONUS aims to make the energy supply cleaner, more secure, and competitive by boosting cost performance and reliability of a broad portfolio of solutions, in line with societal needs and preferences. To this end, CRONUS aims to address the aforementioned challenges through the following specific objectives:

More at cronushorizon.eu/objectives

5 functional prototypes will be developed from optimised lab-scale technological processes

FP1, Athens, Greece

Capture and Utilisation of CO₂ from a biofuels biorefinery that include biomass combustion, ethanolic fermentation and anaerobic digestion via autotrophic algae growth.

This prototype aims to valorise the carbon dioxide produced from three separate streams of an integrated biorefinery. This biorefinery constructed in the framework of Life CircforBio, is situated in NTUA's Lavrion Culture and Technological Park (LCTP), Attica, Greece and treats several types of biowaste with a daily capacity of 1tn wet feedstock. The main products are oil (raw material for biodiesel), bioethanol, biogas and digestate. The pilot includes the following process units: drying, oil extraction, ethanol production unit and anaerobic digestion.

Within this project, the valorization of the biogenic CO₂ produced during the drying process where a biomass burner is used, ethanolic fermentation and anaerobic digestion will be targeted. After the technological processes advanced at lab-scale, the functional prototype 1 will be designed, including the following 3 main stages:

- Efficient dissolution of gaseous CO₂ into aqueous solution, ensuring adequate transfer of CO₂ from the gas phase to the aqueous phase by enzymatic CO₂ capture in the bed reactor.
- Cultivation of algae on the derived solution inside a raceway pond with an inoculation pond included. The produced algae will be harvested by sedimentation as a low-cost harvesting method. A daily production of 1–2 kg of algal biomass is anticipated.
- Valorisation of the produced algal biomass in the existing biorefinery aiming to maximise biofuels production and resource utilization and extraction. Additionally produced algal biomass will be used for the extraction of Carbonic anhydrase enzymes which are used to improve carbon dioxide absorption into water and higher algae production.

PLACE
Athens, Greece

PARTNERS
ALGEN

BIOGENIC GAS
CO₂

BIOGENIC GAS CAPACITY
2000 L/Day

RESPONSIBLE
NTUA

PRODUCTION LINE
**Ethanol Fermentation,
Biodiesel Production,
Anaerobic Digestion**

END-PRODUCT
**Bioethanol,
Biodiesel, Biomass**

TECHNOLOGIES
**Enzymatic Capture Of
CO₂, Autotropic Algae
Cultivation**

FP2, Thessaloniki, Greece

Biological CO₂ hydrogenation for biomethane production.

The demonstration setup will be situated in ELGO facility in Northern Greece and it lies in the conversion of carbon dioxide into methane. Functional Prototype 2 employs a biological method using anaerobic hydrogenotrophic methanogens, which are microorganisms that convert carbon dioxide to methane using induced hydrogen as an electron donor. To produce the necessary hydrogen Functional Prototype 2 utilizes surplus off-peak electricity from renewable sources. Then through electrolysis, the water is split into hydrogen and oxygen.

The produced green hydrogen, together with carbon dioxide derived from a pilot-scale

biogas reactor, is subsequently fed into the Trickle Bed Reactor, which consists of a column filled with a high specific surface area packing material. This provides an ideal environment for microorganisms to attach and grow.

A trickle-feeding strategy creates optimal growth conditions for microorganisms, thus ensuring efficient methane production. The reactor operates in a co-current configuration, allowing biogas from the biogas digester and hydrogen from water electrolysis to be continuously injected, resulting in high-grade biomethane with over 95% methane content.

PLACE
Thessaloniki, Greece

PARTNERS
DTU, UNIPD

BIOGENIC GAS
CO₂

BIOGENIC GAS CAPACITY
330 L/Day

RESPONSIBLE
ELGO

PRODUCTION LINE
Anaerobic Digestion

END-PRODUCT
Biomethane

TECHNOLOGIES
Biological CO₂ Hydrogenation

FP3, Copenhagen, Denmark

Syngas biomethanation

The Functional Prototype 3 will be installed at Copenhagen, Denmark and a robust and reliable technology that directly substitutes natural gas with high-quality biomethane will be developed.

This hybrid process combines thermochemical and biological conversion methods to transform efficiently the remaining organic fraction of anaerobic sludge from biogas plants into valuable biomethane. For achieving this, the key lies in the thermochemical treatment of the remaining organic fraction of anaerobic sludge through pyrolysis, where high temperatures under anaerobic conditions transform the

organic fraction into (synthesis gas) bio-syngas and biochar.

The bio-syngas is upgraded with the necessary amount of hydrogen for full methanation of the biogenic carbon dioxide. Afterwards, it is fed into the syngas biomethanation unit, where the power of anaerobic microbial community comes into play and the bio-syngas, is efficiently converted into natural-gas-grade biomethane.

The bio-syngas biomethanation unit features a trickle bed reactor, continuously fed with both bio-syngas and the liquid fraction of digestate.

PLACE
**Copenhagen,
Denmark**

PARTNERS
BTPRO, CIRAD

BIOGENIC GAS
CO₂, CO, H₂

BIOGENIC GAS CAPACITY
300 L/Day

RESPONSIBLE
DTU

PRODUCTION LINE
Pyrolysis

END-PRODUCT
Biomethane

TECHNOLOGIES
Syngas Biomethanation

FP4, Montpellier, France

Biogenic carbon storage through biochar production

Functional Prototype 4 converts biomass into biochar and bio-fuel gases, through pyrolysis, using high temperatures and the absence of oxygen. Biochar is a porous solid rich in carbon, which offers agronomic benefits and potential carbon sequestration properties.

By optimizing the operating conditions, Functional Prototype 4 produces biochar with high specific surface area for enhanced soil and plant interactions. The pyrolysis reactor is installed on the Energy Platform of BioWooEB Unit. This reactor has

a capacity of 70 L/day. It will be optimized according to the characteristics of the biomass that is used as the raw materials and equipped with a module allowing the production of biochar and the combustion of gases.

The gaseous co-products of the pyrolysis reactor, including CO₂, CO, CH₄, and H₂, possess a high-energy content. These will be collected at the exit of the furnace and then analyzed in order to achieve mass and energy balance.

PLACE
Montpellier, France

PARTNERS
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BIOGENIC GAS
CO, H₂, CH₄, CnH_m

BIOGENIC GAS CAPACITY
600 L/Day

RESPONSIBLE
CIRAD

PRODUCTION LINE
Pyrolysis

END-PRODUCT
Biochar

TECHNOLOGIES
Biogenic Carbon Storage Through Biochar Production

FP5, Boecillo, Spain

Anaerobic digestion system coupled with a microbial electrolysis cell (MEC)

In Functional Prototype 5, a microbial electrolysis cell is coupled with a two-phase anaerobic digestion pilot plant. Anaerobic digestion is a natural process where microorganisms break down organic matter into methane and carbon dioxide. This technology finds application in various sectors, from wastewater treatment plants to the agricultural and process industries. By integrating a microbial electrolysis cell, the FP5 project addresses the challenge of carbon dioxide in biogas.

Microbial electrolysis cells utilize microorganisms to convert carbon dioxide into methane through

electrochemical reactions. This innovative approach maximizes methane production and at the same time reduce the carbon dioxide content in biogas.

The pilot plant consists of a pretreatment unit, an acidification reactor, and a methanogenic reactor. The microbial electrolysis cell can be integrated between the acidification reactor and the methanogenic reactor or directly into the methanogenic reactor. This integration enhances the anaerobic digestion process, reducing carbon dioxide, producing hydrogen, and improving stability.

PLACE
Boecillo, Spain

PARTNERS
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BIOGENIC GAS
CO₂

BIOGENIC GAS CAPACITY
500 L/Day

RESPONSIBLE
CARTIF

PRODUCTION LINE
Anaerobic Digestion

END-PRODUCT
Biomethane

TECHNOLOGIES
In-Situ Biomethanation Using MEC

Progress for each Work Package from December 2022 (M1) until November 2023 (M12) is illustrated in the following graph:

Expected results

EU27 biogenic gas valorisation roadmap

Social value sensitive design and optimisation in the European biofuels sector

Biogenic gas valorisation toolkit

Coupled enzymatic capture of CO₂ with autotrophic algae cultivation

Technology development of biological CO₂ hydrogenation

Technology development of syngas biomethanation

Technology development of biogenic carbon storage

Technology development of pyrolysis and syngas methanation

Technology development of on-situ biomethanation supported by MEC

Microbial resource management

Open access web-developed DSS guiding towards sustainable net-negative biofuel supply chains

Scale up & industrialisation roadmap

Governance briefs

Assessment of viability, feasibility and social acceptance

KICK-OFF MEETING MATERIAL
OF THE PROJECT:
Capture and Reuse Of biogenic gases for
Negative-emission - sustainable biofuels
CRONUS
Project: 101084405 - CRONUS - HORIZON-015-2021-0449

Athens, Monday 12th December 2022

Project events

Kick-off meeting

12/12/2022: The kick-off meeting took place in NTUA premises with the participation of all beneficiaries involved in the project implementation.

H2020 and HE cluster meeting for biofuels and biomethane projects

02/10/2023: The event was organized by CINEA, the European Climate Infrastructure & Environment Executive Agency which supports the implementation of H2020 Programme. Its aim was to present the newly funded Horizon projects on biofuels and biomethane. CRONUS was presented by Dimitris Malamis.

Upcoming events

1st Communities of Practices meeting March 2024

To be announced

11th International Conference on Sustainable Solid Waste Management

June 2024 Rhodes

Learn more: rhodes2024.uest.gr

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2021-D3-03

Research on Sustainability Transitions

The overall approach is built on insights from research on 'sustainability transitions' that analyses innovation within socio-technical systems.

13 partners from 8 countries

The project will be delivered by 13 participant organisations representing 8 European countries

5 Functional Prototypes

Functional prototypes developed from optimised lab-scale technological processes will be designed, constructed and tested

Call: Sustainable, secure and competitive energy supply (HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03)
Project number: 101084405
Duration: 45 months

Starting date: 01/12/2022
End date: 31/08/2026
Budget (EU contribution): 4,390,894.50 €

Coordinating Beneficiary

Associated Beneficiaries

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DI PADOVA

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